

Keywords:

#data, #OpenScience, #ResearchDataManagement, #citizenscience, #DataInfrastructure, #EOSCinPractice, #cross-disciplinary

Implementing a seamless data transfer mechanism between different Research institutions

An EOSC in Practice Story where has been implemented a tool to access and share valuable data across borders and institutions.

The Project Involved

DICE (DATA INFRASTRUCTURE CAPACITY FOR EOSC) is a European Horizon 2020 project funded under Grant Agreement no 101017207. The project aims to develop and improve data management infrastructure for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The project goal is to create an integrated and sustainable infrastructure that will enable researchers to access, share, and preserve research data more efficiently. DICE brings together a consortium of partners from across Europe to develop new tools, services, and policies for data management, and to work towards a more open and collaborative research environment.

CompBioMed, an EU-funded Centre of Excellence in Computational Biomedicine is focused on the use and development of computational methods for biomedical applications. The need for safe data replication and large data transfer between HPC centres, supporting a FAIR data cycle, and the strive to use existing tools for data management within the EU has resulted in a collaboration to set up a B2SAFE federation among HPC centres as core partners in CompBioMed.

The Challenge

The main challenge addressed by the federated B2SAFE service is the lack of a seamless data transfer mechanism between different institutions, which has hindered collaboration and research progress. The ability to share data sets across borders and institutions is essential for researchers to build on each other's work, ultimately leading to more impactful and innovative research. Besides the technical solution that we put in place, there are still challenges from legal and governance perspectives that need to be addressed for sharing data such as having risk assessments and data-sharing agreements between centres.

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"The lack of a seamless data transfer mechanism between different institutions has hindered collaboration and research progress. B2SAFE service enables seamless data transfer between the institutions, making it easier for researchers to access and share valuable data across borders and institutions"

The Users

This EOSC in practice story targets three main types of users: (1) **citizens and citizen scientists** who gather significant data, (2) **researchers** who utilize and gain advantages from the data obtained through smartphones and sensors by citizens, and (3) **software developers**.

The solution

In 2023, the federation of the B2SAFE service by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), University College London (UCL), and SURF (the Dutch national e-infrastructure provider) represents a significant milestone in the research and innovation landscape. The seamless data transfer enabled by the federated B2SAFE service makes it easier for researchers to access and share valuable data across borders and institutions, facilitating collaboration and knowledge exchange. This achievement demonstrates the growing importance of international collaboration in research, as well as the critical role played by advanced data management services like B2SAFE in supporting research excellence and innovation. The federated B2SAFE service provides researchers with a powerful tool to overcome the barriers to data sharing and collaboration, ultimately accelerating the pace of scientific discovery and innovation.

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The service providers

The Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) is a research center that specializes in high-performance computing, data analytics, and artificial intelligence. It is located in Barcelona, Spain and collaborates with national and international partners on various scientific projects.

SURF, is the Dutch national infrastructure provider that support for supports research and education in the Netherlands. SURF is a service provides for the B2SAFE service and contributes in internation projects related to EOSC.

UCL is a university with over 16,000 staff and 50,000 students enaged in teaching and research across a broad range of academic disciplines. It is home to a significant proportion of the research being undertaken as part of the CompBioMed projects. It's institutional data management infrastructure is used to store and process some of the project's data, including sensitive data held on the UCL Data Safe Haven.

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC has emerged as a game-changer in the research community, providing unparalleled visibility and accessibility to research projects across Europe. With an emphasis on interoperability, EOSC has opened up new avenues for collaboration and data sharing, making research more efficient and effective. B2SAFE service play a crucial role in enabling researchers to manage and share their data securely and efficiently, while also catering to the specific requirements of various specialized disciplines. CompBioMed is one of the communities that has participated in a pilot to setup the federated network of B2SAFE nodes, with an aim to help streamlining data management and enhance research outcomes.

The impact on society

The federated B2SAFE service is a powerful tool that not only benefits its target users but also has the potential to create a broader positive impact on society. The ability to facilitate seamless data transfer and collaboration between researchers from different institutions can accelerate the pace of scientific discovery and innovation, leading to the development of new technologies, treatments, and solutions that benefit society at large. The federated nature of the B2SAFE service further enhances its capabilities, allowing it to connect researchers across different regions and disciplines, promoting collaboration and sharing of knowledge. As a result, the B2SAFE service has the potential to play a critical role in addressing some of the most pressing challenges facing society today.

Useful material related to this story

DICE.eu

Across disciplines

In addition to supporting its target users, the federated B2SAFE service has significant potential in promoting cross-disciplinary research initiatives. By enabling researchers from different disciplines to collaborate and share their data sets seamlessly, B2SAFE can break down the silos between different fields, leading to the integration of knowledge and expertise from various domains. This cross-disciplinary collaboration can ultimately lead to the development of more innovative and impactful research, with the potential to address some of the most pressing challenges facing society today. The federated nature of B2SAFE further enhances its capabilities in promoting cross-disciplinary research, as it can connect researchers from different regions and institutions and foster a more collaborative research ecosystem.

Future developments

B2SAFE can be expanded with new features, like the federation with other repositories, the connection with other data management services like B2SHARE and B2FIND, to complete the lifecycle of the data.

Sustainability for an EOSC in practice

B2SAFE is meant to be used as large mid-long term storage for data exploitation. The cost of the service has been partially covered by the INFRA-DEV-07 DICE EC project, under Virtual Access, until the end of the project.

Future funding model scenarios

For BSC, the VA mechanism has been just the entry mechanism, but it is not sustainable, given the mid-long term nature of the data service. The service in Spain can be provided within the data management services of the RES (Spanish Supercomputing Network) free at the point of use for Spanish research groups.

SURF offers the B2SAFE and its federations as a service in production. The service is connected to the tape archive in the backend for long-term preservation of the stored data. The VA mechanism was used during the DICE project for granting access. After that requests for access can be made through computing and data services calls funded by the Dutch National Funding Organisation for Research (NWO) via this [portal](#).

Other providers federated with our storage have their own specific financial plan.

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